

Code and data for reproducing record-statistics

Rasmus E. Benestad

2023-11-09/2024-07-08

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1 Introduction

This document should be regarded as a sort of “lab notebook” that documents the analysis and offers both transparency, reproducibility and may perhaps motivate/assist others carrying out similar work. The analysis was carried out in the R-environment (R Core Team (2020)) and in R-studio.

This analysis is based on the idea of comparing the counted number of record-breaking cases (a record-breaking event is defined as the observation at time t that has a greater value than all of those preceding it: $x_t > [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{t-1}]$) with the number we would expect if the data were independent and identically distributed (iid) as suggested by Benestad (2003). The same kind of analysis was applied to 17 different global climate model (GCM) simulations of monthly precipitation for CMIP3 (SRES A1b, B1 and A2) data by Benestad (2006), and the idea was taken further by Benestad (2008) who used such an iid-test to indicate trends in extremes by testing for shifts in the tails of the statistical distribution. Despite its simplicity and mathematical clarity, iid-tests are still not widespread and have not been carried out for recent global climate model (CMIP5 and CMIP6) results. The simplicity of the iid-test makes it suitable for analysing big data and hundreds of GCM simulations, as we show below.

This document is an R-markdown script that should be regarded as a kind of lab notebook for the numerical analysis that will be used as a deeper level of supporting material (code and data in addition to “lab notes”) for a scientific article on the results. It will provide transparency of the analysis and make the results reproducible/replicable.

This analysis uses some functions from the esd-package for some of the calculations. More information about this open-source R-package can be found from <https://github.com/metno/esd/wiki>.

1.1 The implementation of the analysis

```
## Loading required package: ncdf4
## Loading required package: zoo
##
## Attaching package: 'zoo'
##
## The following objects are masked from 'package:base':
##
##   as.Date, as.Date.numeric
##
## Registered S3 methods overwritten by 'esd':
##   method      from
##   subset.matrix base
##   subset.zoo   zoo
##
## R version 4.4.1 (2024-06-14)
## Platform: x86_64-pc-linux-gnu
## Running under: Ubuntu 22.04.4 LTS
##
## Matrix products: default
## BLAS:   /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/openblas-pthread/libblas.so.3
## LAPACK: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/openblas-pthread/libopenblas-p-r0.3.20.so; LAPACK version 3.10.0
##
## locale:
## [1] LC_CTYPE=en_US.UTF-8      LC_NUMERIC=C
## [3] LC_TIME=nb_NO.UTF-8       LC_COLLATE=en_US.UTF-8
## [5] LC_MONETARY=nb_NO.UTF-8   LC_MESSAGES=en_US.UTF-8
## [7] LC_PAPER=nb_NO.UTF-8      LC_NAME=C
## [9] LC_ADDRESS=C              LC_TELEPHONE=C
## [11] LC_MEASUREMENT=nb_NO.UTF-8 LC_IDENTIFICATION=C
##
## time zone: Europe/Oslo
## tzcode source: system (glibc)
##
## attached base packages:
## [1] stats      graphics  grDevices  utils      datasets  methods    base
##
## other attached packages:
## [1] esd_1.10.86 zoo_1.8-12  ncdf4_1.22
##
## loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
## [1] digest_0.6.35 fastmap_1.1.1 xfun_0.43      lattice_0.22-5
## [5] knitr_1.46      htmltools_0.5.8.1 rmarkdown_2.26 cli_3.6.2
## [9] grid_4.4.1      compiler_4.4.1  rstudioapi_0.16.0 tools_4.4.1
## [13] evaluate_0.23   yaml_2.3.8      rlang_1.1.3
```

1.1.1 Functions

The following chunk sets up a function for estimating the statistics of record-breaking events, using iid (independent and identically distributed) data as a baseline:

```
## Count the number of record-breaking events and compare with expected number from iid
percent.records <- function(x,it=1:12,na.rm=TRUE,setattr=TRUE,verbose=FALSE) {
  if (verbose) print(match.call())
  if (verbose) print(class(x))
}
```

```

d <- dim(x)
rstat <- matrix(rep(NA,d[2]*12),12,d[2])
if (inherits(x,'month')) {
  for (i in it) {
    if (verbose) print(month.abb[i])
    y <- subset(x,it=month.abb[i])
    n.obs <- unlist(n.records(y)$N)
    if (verbose) print(summary(n.obs))
    n.iid <- sum(1/(1:length(index(y))))
    if (verbose) print(n.iid)
    rstat[i,] <- 100*n.obs/n.iid
  }
  rstat <- colMeans(rstat,na.rm=TRUE)
  if (setattr) rstat <- attrcp(x,rstat)
} else {
  n.obs <- unlist(n.records(x)$N)
  n.iid <- sum(1/(1:length(index(x))))
  rstat <- 100*n.obs/n.iid
}
attr(rstat,'variable') <- paste(varid(x),'records',sep=' * ')
attr(rstat,'unit') <- "%'"
attr(rstat,'n.iid') <- n.iid
attr(rstat,'period') <- paste(min(index(x)),max(index(x)),sep=' - ')
if (setattr) {
  dim(rstat) <- attr(x,'dimensions')[1:2]
  attr(rstat,'longitude') <- lon(x)
  attr(rstat,'latitude') <- lat(x)
}
return(rstat)
}

## Lag-one correlation (violates iid)
AR1 <- function(x,it=1:12) {
  print(match.call())
  print(class(x))
  d <- dim(x)
  rstat <- matrix(rep(NA,d[2]*12),12,d[2])
  if (inherits(x,'month')) {
    for (i in it) {
      #print(month.abb[i])
      y <- subset(x,it=month.abb[i])
      rstat[i,] <- apply(y,2,function(x) acf(x,plot=FALSE)$acf[2])
    }
    rstat <- colMeans(rstat)
    rstat <- attrcp(x,rstat)
  } else {
    n.obs <- apply(y,2,function(x) acf(x,plot=FALSE)$acf[2])
  }
  attr(rstat,'variable') <- paste(varid(x),'AR(1)',sep=' * ')
  attr(rstat,'unit') <- "correlation"
  dim(rstat) <- attr(x,'dimensions')[1:2]
  attr(rstat,'longitude') <- lon(x)
  attr(rstat,'latitude') <- lat(x)
}

```

```

return(rstat)
}

retrieverecords <- function(fname) {
  ## Get the grid and times
  x <- map(retrieve(fname,it=c(2022,2022)),plot=FALSE)
  tmp.file <- paste0('retrieverecords.',varid(x),'.rda')
  high <- x; low <- x
  high.djf <- x; low.djf <- x
  high.mam <- x; low.mam <- x
  high.jja <- x; low.jja <- x
  high.son <- x; low.son <- x
  ar1 <- x;
  trend <- x; mean <- x
  trend.djf <- x; mean.djf <- x
  trend.mam <- x; mean.mam <- x
  trend.jja <- x; mean.jja <- x
  trend.son <- x; mean.son <- x
  x <- retrieve(fname,lon=c(0,2),lat=c(0,2))
  tim <- index(x)
  ## Now read the data piece-wise
  ncid <- nc_open(fname)
  nt <- ncid$dim[[1]]$len
  nx <- ncid$dim[[2]]$len
  ny <- ncid$dim[[3]]$len
  print(paste('Reading',names(ncid$var)[1]))
  if (file.exists(tmp.file)) {
    load(tmp.file)
    i1 <- i
  } else i1 <- 1
  for (i in i1:nx) {
    y <- nvar_get(ncid,names(ncid$var)[1],start=c(i,1,1),count=c(1,ny,nt))
    y <- zoo(t(y),order.by=tim)
    class(y) <- c('field','month','zoo')
    ## annual
    rh <- percent.records(y,it=1:12,setattr=FALSE,verbose=FALSE)
    rl <- percent.records(-y,it=1:12,setattr=FALSE,verbose=FALSE)
    high[i,] <- rh
    low[i,] <- rl
    trend[i,] <- apply(annual(y),2,'trend.coef')
    mean[i,] <- apply(annual(y),2,'mean',na.rm=TRUE)
    ## Different seasons
    rh <- percent.records(y,it=c(12,1,2),setattr=FALSE,verbose=FALSE)
    rl <- percent.records(-y,it=c(12,1,2),setattr=FALSE,verbose=FALSE)
    high.djf[i,] <- rh
    low.djf[i,] <- rl
    ys <- annual(subset(y,it=month.abb[c(12,1,2)]),nmin=3)
    trend.djf[i,] <- apply(ys,2,'trend.coef')
    mean.djf[i,] <- apply(ys,2,'mean',na.rm=TRUE)
    rh <- percent.records(y,it=3:5,setattr=FALSE,verbose=FALSE)
    rl <- percent.records(-y,it=3:5,setattr=FALSE,verbose=FALSE)
    high.mam[i,] <- rh
    low.mam[i,] <- rl
  }
}

```

```

ys <- annual(subset(y,it=month.abb[3:5]),nmin=3)
trend.mam[i,] <- apply(ys,2,'trend.coef')
mean.mam[i,] <- apply(ys,2,'mean',na.rm=TRUE)
rh <- percent.records(y,it=6:8,setattr=FALSE,verbose=FALSE)
rl <- percent.records(-y,it=6:8,setattr=FALSE,verbose=FALSE)
high.jja[i,] <- rh
low.jja[i,] <- rl
ys <- annual(subset(y,it=month.abb[6:8]),nmin=3)
trend.jja[i,] <- apply(ys,2,'trend.coef')
mean.jja[i,] <- apply(ys,2,'mean',na.rm=TRUE)
rh <- percent.records(y,it=9:11,setattr=FALSE,verbose=FALSE)
rl <- percent.records(-y,it=9:11,setattr=FALSE,verbose=FALSE)
high.son[i,] <- rh
low.son[i,] <- rl
ys <- annual(subset(y,it=month.abb[9:11]),nmin=3)
trend.son[i,] <- apply(ys,2,'trend.coef')
mean.son[i,] <- apply(ys,2,'mean',na.rm=TRUE)
ar1[i,] <- AR1(y)
save(i,high,low,high.djf,high.mam,high.jja,high.son,low.djf,low.mam,low.jja,low.son,
     trend,trend.djf,trend.mam,trend.jja,trend.son,mean,mean.djf,mean.mam,mean.jja,mean.son,
     ar1=ar1,file=tmp.file)
print(paste0('< ',tmp.file,' > ',i,'/',nx,' +++   range mean DJF:',
            min(mean[i,]),'-',max(mean[i,])))
}
nc_close(ncid)
results <- list(high=high,low=low,trend=trend,mean=mean,
               high.djf=high.djf,high.mam=high.mam,
               high.jja=high.jja,high.son=high.son,
               low.djf=low.djf,low.mam=low.mam,
               low.jja=low.jja,low.son=low.son,
               trend.djf=trend.djf,trend.mam=trend.mam,
               trend.jja=trend.jja,trend.son=trend.son,
               mean.djf=mean.djf,mean.mam=mean.mam,
               mean.jja=mean.jja,mean.son=mean.son,
               ar1=ar1)
attr(results,'variable') <- paste(varid(x),'records',sep=' * ')
attr(results,'unit') <- "count"
attr(results,'period') <- paste(min(tim),max(tim),sep=' - ')
file.remove(tmp.file)
return(results)
}

list2field <- function(x,it='annual',plot=FALSE, verbose=FALSE,...) {
  #print('list2field')
  cn <- names(x)
  if (!is.null(it)) if (is.character(it)) cn <- names(x)[grep(it,names(x))]
  n <- length(cn)
  #print(cn)
  Y <- x[['ERA5']]
  lons <- lon(Y)
  iw <- lons > 180; lons[iw] <- lons[iw] - 360
  attr(Y,'longitude') <- lons
  nxy <- length(Y)

```

```

X <- matrix(rep(NA,n*nxy),n+1,nxy)
X[1,] <- c(Y)
for (i in 1:n) {
  z <- x[[cn[i]]]
  lons <- lon(z)
  iw <- lons > 180; lons[iw] <- lons[iw] - 360
  attr(z,'longitude') <- lons
  z <- regrid(z,is=Y)
  X[i+1,] <- c(z)
  if (verbose) print(paste(i,': ',cn[i],'lenth=',length(z),'mean=',
                           round(mean(c(z),na.rm=TRUE),2)))
}

X <- as.field(zoo(X,order.by=1:n),param='record-rate',
             unit="%",lon=lon(Y),lat=lat(Y),
             info='record maps: list2field',longname='record-breaking events')

if (plot) map(X,FUN='sd',
             main='Multi-modal ensemble trend spread (CMIP6)',sub='1959-2021')
par(new=FALSE)
#par(fig=c(0,0.3,0,0.3),new=TRUE)
#hist(c(r),lwd=3,col=rgb(0,0,0,0.5))
attr(X,'ID') <- cn
invisible(X)
}

mapofrecords <- function(x,main='map',colbar=list()) {
  breaks <- c(seq(50,90,length=5),100,seq(110,300,length=20))
  col <- colbar$col
  rev <- colbar$rev; if (is.null(rev)) rev <- FALSE
  if (is.null(col))
    col <- c(colscal(n=10,pal='t2m.ipcc',rev=rev)[1:5],rgb(1,1,1),rgb(1,1,1),
             colscal(n=40,pal='t2m.ipcc',rev=rev)[21:40]) else
    if (col=='dry2wet')
      col <- c(colscal(n=10,pal='precip.ipcc')[1:5],rgb(1,1,1),rgb(1,1,1),
             colscal(n=40,pal='precip.ipcc')[21:40]) else
      if (col=='wet2dry')
        col <- c(rev(colscal(n=10,pal='precip.ipcc')[6:10]),
                rgb(1,1,1),rgb(1,1,1),
                rev(colscal(n=40,pal='precip.ipcc')[1:20]))

  if (length(grep('breaks',names(colbar)))==0) colbar[['breaks']] <- breaks else
    breaks <- colbar[['breaks']]
  if (length(grep('col',names(colbar)))==0) {
    colbar[['col']] <- col
  } else if (is.character(colbar[['col']])) colbar[['col']] <- col
  attr(x,'variable') <- 'ratio'
  attr(x,'unit') <- "%"
  m <- map(x,plot=FALSE)
  attr(m,'variable') <- 'zeta'
  attr(m,'unit') <- paste(varid(x),"%")
  attr(m,'period') <- attr(x,'period')
  m[m < min(breaks)] <- min(breaks); m[m > max(breaks)] <- max(breaks)
}

```

```

map(m,projection="+proj=robin",colbar=colbar,main=main,type='fill',verbose=FALSE)
invisible(m)
}

globalMean <- function(x) {
  d <- dim(x)
  w <- cos(pi*lat(x)/180)
  a <- t(matrix(rep(w,d[1]),d[2],d[1]))
  xw <- x*a
  xm <- sum(xw)/sum(a)
  return(xm)
}

```

2 Processing of historical observations

Two different reanalyses (NCEP2 Kalnay et al. (1996) and ERA5 Hersbach and Dee (2016)) were assessed here to get an indication of the robustness of these results. If the results diverge substantially, then that would indicate that there are data issues that need to be addressed and that the derived record-breaking statistics may not necessarily reflect real world tendencies.

2.1 Monthly mean NCEP2 reanalysis and ERA5 reanalysis

The NCEP2 reanalysis provides coarser information than ERA5, which has a spatial resolution of ~30 km. The difference in the resolution explains the different sizes of data volumes, which also dictated two different processing strategies - the NCEP2 data could be analysed in one go whereas the ERA5 was processed in chunks.

The chunk of R-code below does the calculations and produces the results. Since the data processing takes some time, the data is saved in a temporary file. This chunk also shows how the processing was done line-by-line. Intermediate results were saved in temporary files to resume calculations in case of interruptions. The results of this processing are stored in a R-binary file stored in the working directory to save time and energy. This binary-file will also be shared with this code.

```

## Temporary file name for storing the results and sharing necessary data for replication
## This chunk takes some time to do...
fname <- '~/R/record.stats.rda'
if (!file.exists(fname)) {
  t2m <- retrieve('~Downloads/air.mon.mean.nc')
  print(range(index(t2m)))
  ## Annual
  high.t2m.record.stats <- percent.records(t2m)
  low.t2m.record.stats <- percent.records(-t2m)
  ar1.t2m.stats <- AR1(t2m)
  ## Winter
  high.t2m.record.stats.djf <- percent.records(t2m,it=c(12,1,2))
  low.t2m.record.stats.djf <- percent.records(-t2m,it=c(12,1,2))
  ## Spring
  high.t2m.record.stats.mam <- percent.records(t2m,it=3:5)
  low.t2m.record.stats.mam <- percent.records(-t2m,it=3:5)
  high.t2m.record.stats.jja <- percent.records(t2m,it=6:8)
  low.t2m.record.stats.jja <- percent.records(-t2m,it=6:8)
  ## Autumn
  high.t2m.record.stats.son <- percent.records(t2m,it=9:11)
  low.t2m.record.stats.son <- percent.records(-t2m,it=9:11)
}

```

```

##
## ERA5 - annually aggregated values to limit computational demands
T2M <- retrieverecords('~data/ERA5/ERA5_t2m_mon.nc')
TP <- retrieverecords('~data/ERA5/ERA5_tp_mon.nc')

save(t2m,high.t2m.record.stats,low.t2m.record.stats,
     high.t2m.record.stats.djf,low.t2m.record.stats.djf,
     high.t2m.record.stats.mam,low.t2m.record.stats.mam,
     high.t2m.record.stats.jja,low.t2m.record.stats.jja,
     high.t2m.record.stats.son,low.t2m.record.stats.son,
     T2M,TP,file=fname)
} else load(fname)

```

Moreover, due to the large data volumes of ERA5, the data had to be processed chunk-wise and the organisation of the results for the latter years didn't align correctly with the grid coordinates of the early years (different longitude layouts). Perhaps some of the data processing changed between the times that the different files were fetched from Copernicus C3S (e.g. improved/changed routines). Therefore, the following chunk of code ensures that the coordinates (longitudes) are correct and consistent for all years:

```

irs <- names(T2M)
for (ir in irs) {
  z <- T2M[[ir]]
  attr(z,'longitude') <- lon(z) + 180
  west <- attr(z,'longitude') > 180
  attr(z,'longitude')[west] <- attr(z,'longitude')[west] - 360
  attr(z,'latitude') <- rev(lat(z))
  attr(z,'period') <- attr(T2M,'period')
  z -> T2M[[ir]]
}
irs <- names(TP)
for (ir in irs) {
  z <- TP[[ir]]
  attr(z,'longitude') <- lon(z) + 180
  west <- attr(z,'longitude') > 180
  attr(z,'longitude')[west] <- attr(z,'longitude')[west] - 360
  attr(z,'latitude') <- rev(lat(z))
  attr(z,'period') <- attr(TP,'period')
  z -> TP[[ir]]
}

```

3 Results - figures

This section presents diagnostics of the results of this analysis. The rate of record-breaking recurrences is defined as $\zeta = 100 \times n_{obs}/n_{iid}$, where n_{obs} is the count of observed record-breaking events and n_{iid} is the expected number of record-breaking recurrences if the data is independent and identically distributed (iid). The statistics of recurrence of records is discussed in e.g. Benestad (2003) and Benestad (2008).

3.1 The NCEP reanalysis

Results for monthly mean temperature from the NCEP reanalysis. The analysis of the records was done on all calendar months respectively, and then the annual mean was estimated as the average from these monthly results. Taking the mean over the calendar months will smooth over random fluctuations to some degree, improving the signal-to-noise ratio. A colour scale is used, with warmer temperatures shown in red and colder temperatures in blue. For the statistics of record-low temperatures, the colour scale is reversed (more

record-low events indicate cooler conditions).

The chunk below presents three figures: the record-breaking recurrence of high temperatures, low temperatures and the mean linear trend representing mean temperatures (based on an ordinary linear regression OLR against time):

```
n.iid <- attr(high.t2m.record.stats,'n.iid')
high.t2m <- mapofrecords(high.t2m.record.stats,
                        main='NCEP2 High records annual temperature (1948-2022)')
```

```
## Loading required package: sf
```

```
## Linking to GEOS 3.10.2, GDAL 3.4.1, PROJ 8.2.1; sf_use_s2() is TRUE
```

```
## Loading required package: oce
```

```
## Loading required package: gsw
```

NCEP2 High records annual temperature (1948-2022)


```
## Note that the colours have been reversed so that red marks warmer trends (less cold records)
low.t2m <- mapofrecords(low.t2m.record.stats,colbar=list(pal='t2m.ipcc',rev=TRUE),
                      main='NCEP Low records annual temperature (1948-2022)')
```

NCEP Low records annual temperature (1948-2022)


```
trend.t2m <- map(annual(t2m),FUN='trend',projection="+proj=robin",  
                colbar=list(breaks=seq(-1.2,1.2,by=0.1),pal='t2m.ipcc'),  
                type='fill')
```


The highest rate of record-warm months is seen in the tropics, and the number of record-cold months is also low in the tropics (note that the colors have been reversed, with red indicating warming conditions). The high number of record-warm months has a different geographical distribution to that of the linear trend, which is strongest in the Arctic.

3.1.1 Sensitivity to the time interval

We can explore how the choice of time period influences the estimated record recurrence rate ζ . Since the NCEP2 reanalysis has smaller volumes than ERA5 and allows faster analysis, we carried out a sensitivity test for the time interval based on the NCEP2 reanalysis in the chunk of R code below.

```
## Early part of the data record: 1948-1980
t2m <- retrieve('~Downloads/air.mon.mean.nc',it=c(1948,1980))

## [1] "Warning : Calendar attribute has not been found in the meta data and will be set automatically."
mapofrecords(percent.records(t2m),
              main='NCEP2 High records annual temperature (1948-1980)')
```

NCEP2 High records annual temperature (1948-1980)


```
t2m <- retrieve('~Downloads/air.mon.mean.nc',it=c(1960,2022))
```

```
## [1] "Warning : Calendar attribute has not been found in the meta data and will be set automatically."
```

```
mapofrecords(percent.records(t2m),  
              main='NCEP2 High records annual temperature (1960-2022)')
```

NCEP2 High records annual temperature (1960-2022)


```
t2m <- retrieve('~Downloads/air.mon.mean.nc',it=c(1980,2022))
```

```
## [1] "Warning : Calendar attribute has not been found in the meta data and will be set automatically."
```

```
mapofrecords(percent.records(t2m),  
             main='NCEP2 High records annual temperature (1980-2022)')
```

NCEP2 High records annual temperature (1980-2022)


```
t2m <- retrieve('~Downloads/air.mon.mean.nc',it=c(1991,2020))
```

```
## [1] "Warning : Calendar attribute has not been found in the meta data and will be set automatically."
```

```
mapofrecords(percent.records(t2m),  
             main='NCEP2 High records annual temperature (1991-2020)')
```

NCEP2 High records annual temperature (1991-2020)

The results of the sensitivity tests suggests low record-high recurrence rates in the early part of the NCEP2 data 1948–1980, and especially over northern hemisphere land. Low recurrence rates were also estimated over extended maritime regions in the southern hemisphere for the time eriod 1980–2023, but the recurrence rates for 1960–2023 were generally similar to those for the full 1948–2023 period. The recurrence rate estimated for the most recent normal period 1991–2020 indicated lower recurrence rates, but 30 years is expected to be more influenced by natural decadal variability than longer intervals.

3.2 The ERA5 reanalysis

The analysis was repeated using ERA5 for a different period (1950-2023) and applied to the four seasons (Dec-Feb, Mar-May, Jun-Aug and Sep-Nov) separately to determine if opposite trends in different seasons may have cancelled out in the annual mean. The seasonal results also provide justification for using only the annual statistics if there are no substantial differences between the seasonal and annual analyses.

3.2.1 Record statistics of hot years and seasons

```
high.T2m.ERA5.record.stats <- T2M[['high']]  
mapofrecords(high.T2m.ERA5.record.stats,main='ERA5 High records: annual temperature')
```

ERA5 High records: annual temperature


```
print('Summary of the record map:')  
  
## [1] "Summary of the record map:"  
print(summary(c(high.T2m.ERA5.record.stats)))  
  
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.   
##  27.28 115.93  131.27  132.72  148.32  308.58  
for (is in c('djf','mam','jja','son')) {  
  par(mfcol=c(1,1))  
  mapofrecords(T2M[[paste0("high.",is)]],main=paste('ERA5',toupper(is),'High records'))  
}
```

ERA5 DJF High records

ERA5 MAM High records

ERA5 JJA High records

ERA5 SON High records

The recurrence of record-breaking annual mean temperatures in ERA5 has some similarities to those derived from NCEP2 reanalysis, such as higher rates of recurrences over the Indian Ocean and the western tropical Pacific. There is a pronounced discrepancy over central Africa with lower rates of recurrences in the ERA5 data, however. There are no substantial differences between seasons, justifying the use of annual statistics for the subsequent analysis.

3.2.2 Traditional trend analyses

Maps of trends for the entire year and the seasons provide similar information as for NCEP2, with no substantial differences between the seasons. The strongest warming is seen in the Arctic, particularly associated with sea ice retreat.

```
map(T2M[['trend']], colbar=list(breaks=seq(-1.2,1.2,by=0.1),pal='t2m.ipcc'),  
    main=paste('ERA5 annual trend'),type='fill',projection="+proj=robin")
```

ERA5 annual trend


```
for (is in c('djf','mam','jja','son')) {  
  par(mfcol=c(1,1))  
  map(T2M[[paste0("trend.",is)]],  
      colbar=list(breaks=seq(-1.75,1.75,by=0.25),pal='t2m.ipcc'),  
      main=paste('ERA5',toupper(is),'trend'),type='fill',projection="+proj=robin")  
}
```

ERA5 DJF trend

ERA5 MAM trend

ERA5 JJA trend

ERA5 SON trend

In other words, the geographical distribution of the strongest trends in the mean temperature differ from the highest recurrences of record-breaking years and seasons. The former is sensitive to the marginal changes whereas the latter is more sensitive to persistence and the degree to which the trend is monotonous.

3.2.3 Record statistics of cold years and seasons

In the chunk below, the order of colours has been reversed for the recurrences of record-low temperatures. The results from ERA5 are similar to those from NCEP2, albeit with some differences in the warm pool area (the western tropical Pacific), central Africa and the Southern Sea south of Africa. In general, there is a deficiency of cold annual/seasonal temperature records in the tropics, which can be interpreted as a shift of the lower tail of the distribution towards higher temperatures.

```
low.T2m.ERA5.record.stats <- T2M[['low']]
mapofrecords(low.T2m.ERA5.record.stats,colbar=list(rev=TRUE),
             main='ERA5 low records: annual temperature')
```

ERA5 low records: annual temperature


```
print('Summary of the record map:')  
  
## [1] "Summary of the record map:"  
print(summary(c(low.T2m.ERA5.record.stats)))  
  
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.   Max.   
##  25.57  78.42   88.65   89.72 100.59  158.55  
  
for (is in c('djf','mam','jja','son')) {  
  par(mfcol=c(1,1))  
  mapofrecords(T2M[[paste0("low.",is)]],colbar=list(rev=TRUE),  
              main=paste('ERA5',toupper(is),'low records'))  
}
```

ERA5 DJF low records

ERA5 MAM low records

ERA5 JJA low records

ERA5 SON low records

The maps of ζ for record-low annual mean temperature show low numbers over the tropical oceans (marked red as these regions are warmer with fewer record-cold events) and moderately high values over the North Atlantic. For Dec-Jan, there are relatively high ζ over parts of North America, possibly related to the polar vortex and cold outbreaks with frigid polar air masses.

An increase in ζ for both record-hot and record-cold seasons/years indicates that the range of variability (standard deviation) has increased over time. However, over parts of the North Atlantic, there have been lower ζ for record-warm and higher ζ for record-cold seasons/years, in line with a regional cooling, which may be linked to ocean circulation.

3.2.4 Mean temperatures

We also plot the maps of mean temperatures with data that have been processed exactly the same way as the records to check that the post-processing (geographical arrangement of the grid boxes) is correct. One clue is the low temperatures over mountain ranges such as the Himalayas and the Andes, as seen in the maps below:

```
for (is in c('djf','mam','jja','son')) {  
  par(mfcol=c(1,1))  
  map(T2M[[paste0("mean.",is)]]- 273.15,  
      colbar=list(breaks=seq(-40,40,by=4),pal='t2m.ipcc'),
```

```
main=paste(toupper(is),'mean'),type='fill',projection="+proj=robin")
}
```

DJF mean

MAM mean

JJA mean

SON mean

The processing for the mean temperatures was the same as for the record recurrences and trends, and these maps show well-known global geographical distributions of temperature, with colder conditions at higher latitudes and altitudes. A motivation for the check was the need to split the processing into smaller chunks (due to data size and memory limitations). Thus these maps provide a quality check for the other statistics presented here.

3.2.5 The geographical distribution of autocorrelation

```
ar1.t2m <- map(T2M[["ar1"]],main='AR(1) for temperature',type='fill',projection="+proj=robin")
```

AR(1) for temperature

The one-year autocorrelation between seasonal mean temperature is pronounced in parts of the tropics, such as the warm pool over the western tropical Pacific and central Africa, which can at least partly explain the high count of record-breaking seasons and the violation of iid. The high year-to-year auto-correlation may be a result of smooth and gradual change (small margins) or a trend that is not disturbed much by pronounced year-to-year fluctuations. An exception is the cold tongue along the equator off the west coast of Ecuador/Peru, which is strongly influenced by El Nino Southern Oscillation (ENSO).

3.2.6 Statistical summary

The information in the maps can be summarized in terms of the global mean and a histogram.

```
## Record-highs
#rhstats <- c(T2M[['high.djf']],T2M[['high.mam']],T2M[['high.jja']],T2M[['high.son']])
rhstats <- c(T2M[['high']])
print(summary(rhstats))
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
## 27.28 115.93 131.27 132.72 148.32 308.58
```

```
## The area-weighted global mean
print(paste('Area-weighted global mean',globalMean(T2M[['high']])))
```

```
## [1] "Area-weighted global mean 136.004728871304"
```

```
breaks <- seq(0,500,by=10)
cols <- rep('blue',length(breaks))
cols[breaks >= 100] <- 'red'
hist(rhstats,breaks=breaks,col=cols,main='High records',
     xlab='number or record-breaking seasonal rainfall')
```

High records


```
## Record-lows
#rlstats <- c(T2M[['low.djf']],T2M[['low.mam']],T2M[['low.jja']],T2M[['low.son']])
rlstats <- c(T2M[['low']])
print(summary(rlstats))
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
## 25.57  78.42   88.65   89.72 100.59 158.55
```

```
## The area-weighted global mean
print(paste('Area-weighted global mean',globalMean(T2M[['low']])))
```

```
## [1] "Area-weighted global mean 88.3909332550489"
```

```
cols <- rep('blue',length(breaks))
cols[breaks < 100] <- 'red'
hist(rlstats,breaks=breaks,col=cols,main='Low records',
     xlab='number or record-breaking annual rainfall')
```



```
print(summary(rhstats/rlstats))
```

```
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
## 0.1975 1.2034  1.4600  1.5652  1.8070  8.1176
```

The global statistics of the number of record-warm months indicates that record-warm months are more common than record-cold ones. The high number of record-warm months reflects a tendency towards more hot conditions over the historical period. The count of record-low temperatures is also less than the reference count from iid data.

3.2.7 Area with high temperatures

The fractional global surface area with daily mean temperature exceeding 40°C can be used as an indicator for hot day occurrence. Such an indicator based on ERA5 suggests a strong increase since the 1980s. The curves below provide the annual mean surface area fraction with daily temperatures above the thresholds of

30°C and 40°C, respectively:

```
par(cex.main=0.75)
tgt30 <- subset(
  AreaClimateIndicator(param='t2m',FUN='mean',threshold=30,plot=FALSE),it=c(1950,2023))
tgt40 <- subset(
  AreaClimateIndicator(param='t2m',FUN='mean',threshold=40,plot=FALSE),it=c(1950,2023))
Aref30 <- mean(subset(tgt30,it=c(1951,1980)))
Aref40 <- mean(subset(tgt40,it=c(1951,1980)))
tgt30 <- 100*tgt30/Aref30
tgt40 <- 100*tgt40/Aref40
# https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/planetary/factsheet/earthfact.html
Aearth <- 4*pi*6371^2 ## square km
print(paste('Aref30=',round(Aearth*Aref30),'km^2; Aref40=',round(Aearth*Aref40),'km^2'))
```

```
## [1] "Aref30= 7565377 km^2; Aref40= 4636 km^2"
```

```
plot(merge(tgt30,tgt40),col=c('black','red'),plot.type='single',ylab='%',xlab='',
      main='Fractional area of hot daily temperatures (wrt. 1951-1980)',lwd=2,log='y')
grid()
legend(1950,1500,c(expression(T > 30*degree*C),expression(T > 40*degree*C)),lty=1,
      col=c('black','red'),,lwd=2,bty='n')
```


In other words, this statistics of daily temperatures from ERA5 indicates that hot days anywhere on Earth have become more widespread and severe over time. The curve for 40°C shows a stronger gradient (“acceleration” since 2000) than for 30°C.

For the sake of completeness, we repeated the analysis for hot days and applied it to the global area fraction with daily temperature below -30°C and -40°C respectively:

```
par(cex.main=0.75)
tlt30 <- subset(
  AreaClimateIndicator(param='t2m',FUN='mean',threshold=-30,plot=FALSE),it=c(1950,2023))
tlt40 <- subset(
  AreaClimateIndicator(param='t2m',FUN='mean',threshold=-40,plot=FALSE),it=c(1950,2023))
Aref30 <- mean(subset(tlt30,it=c(1951,1980)))
Aref40 <- mean(subset(tlt40,it=c(1951,1980)))
tlt30 <- 100*tlt30/Aref30
tlt40 <- 100*tlt40/Aref40
print(paste('Aref30=',round(Aearth*Aref30),'km^2; Aref40=',round(Aearth*Aref40),'km^2'))
```

```
## [1] "Aref30= 12485204 km^2; Aref40= 5482269 km^2"
```

```
plot(merge(tlt30,tlt40),col=c('black','red'),plot.type='single',ylab='% ',
      main='Fractional area of cold daily temperatures (wrt. 1951-1980)')
grid()
legend(1950,10,c(expression(T < -30*degree*C),expression(T < -40*degree*C)),lty=1,
      col=c('black','red'),bty='n')
```


3.3 ERA5 precipitation

The analysis of the number of record-breaking seasonal rainfall was based on ERA5, which has a spatial resolution of 32km. Green shading shows wet regions and brown shading marks dry regions (using the same palette as the IPCC).

3.3.1 Annual and seasonal record high statistics

```
high.Tp.ERA5.record.stats <- TP[['high']]
mapofrecords(high.Tp.ERA5.record.stats,colbar=list(col='dry2wet'),
             main='ERA5 High records: annual precipitation')
```

ERA5 High records: annual precipitation


```
print('Summary of the record map:')
```

```
## [1] "Summary of the record map:"
```

```
print(summary(c(high.Tp.ERA5.record.stats)))
```

```
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##  30.77  95.74  105.99  105.93  116.25  186.34
```

```
for (is in c('djf','mam','jja','son')) {  
  mapofrecords(TP[[paste0("high.",is)]],colbar=list(col='dry2wet'),  
              main=paste('ERA5',toupper(is),'high precipitation records'))  
}
```

ERA5 DJF high precipitation records

ERA5 MAM high precipitation records

ERA5 JJA high precipitation records

ERA5 SON high precipitation records

The general picture is that there have been fewer record-breaking high annual rainfall events concentrated over parts of Africa, Latin America, Asia and Indonesia, and more record-wet years over parts of the Southern Ocean and the tropical oceans. The dry conditions are also seen in the high record-low rainfall amounts below. This tendency is also discernible in a regular trend analysis. Regions connected with the Inter-tropical convergence Zone (ITCZ) over the oceans tend to have a higher rate of record-recurrences ζ , perhaps in line with an increased overturning Benestad (2016)? There are also regions at higher latitudes where $\zeta > 100$.

There are more pronounced differences in record-recurrences ζ for precipitation between seasons, but there are no indications of opposite tendencies between the four seasons, which justifies an analysis of the annual precipitation totals/means.

3.3.2 Traditional trend analysis for annual and seasonal precipitation

```
z <- 100*TP[["trend"]]/TP[["mean"]]  
attr(z,'unit') <- "%"  
map(z,colbar=list(breaks=seq(-20,20,by=2),pal='precip.ipcc'),  
     main='Annual precipitation trend',type='fill',projection="+proj=robin")
```

Annual precipitation trend


```
for (is in c('djf','mam','jja','son')) {  
  z <- 100*TP[[paste0("trend.",is)]]/TP[[paste0("mean.",is)]]  
  attr(z,'unit') <- "%"  
  map(z,colbar=list(breaks=seq(-20,20,by=2),pal='precip.ipcc'),  
      main=paste(toupper(is),'precipitation trend'),type='fill',projection="+proj=robin")  
}
```

DJF precipitation trend

MAM precipitation trend

JJA precipitation trend

SON precipitation trend

The geographical patterns of record-breaking recurrences have a tendency to match those of more traditional trend analysis representing mean conditions, with dry regions in the sub-tropics becoming drier.

3.3.3 Annual and seasonal record low statistics

In the following plots for low annual/seasonal precipitation records, green indicates wet.

```
low.Tp.ERA5.record.stats <- TP[['low']]  
mapofrecords(low.Tp.ERA5.record.stats,colbar=list(col='wet2dry'),  
             main='ERA5 low records: annual precipitation')
```

ERA5 low records: annual precipitation


```
print('Summary of the record map:')  
  
## [1] "Summary of the record map:"  
print(summary(c(low.Tp.ERA5.record.stats)))  
  
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.   
##  22.22  83.77   94.03   92.94 102.57  186.34  
for (is in c('djf','mam','jja','son')) {  
  mapofrecords(TP[[paste0("low.",is)]],colbar=list(col='wet2dry'),  
               main=paste(toupper(is),'low precipitation records'))  
}
```

DJF low precipitation records

MAM low precipitation records

JJA low precipitation records

SON low precipitation records

For low annual/seasonal precipitation amounts, there are some suspicious results over parts of Africa (widespread low ζ for record-low annual rainfall). Low ζ for both record-high and record-low annual rainfall in this region suggest that the range of annual variability has diminished.

3.3.4 Auto-correlation AR1

The annual year-to-year AR1 for precipitation was calculated as the average for each of the 12 calendar months.

```
attr(TP[["ar1"]], 'unit') <- 'correlation'  
ar1.tp <- map(TP[["ar1"]], colbar=list(pal='t2m'),  
             main='AR(1) for precipitation', type='fill', projection="+proj=robin")
```

AR(1) for precipitation

The AR1 values for precipitation were generally low except for parts of Africa. There seem to be some issues with the simulation of rainfall over Africa in the reanalysis, which may be connected to data availability and quality.

3.3.5 Statistical summary

```
## Record-highs
#rhstats <- c(TP[['high.djf']],TP[['high.mam']],TP[['high.jja']],TP[['high.son']])
rhstats <- c(TP[['high']])
print(summary(rhstats))
```

```
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##  30.77  95.74  105.99  105.93  116.25  186.34
```

```
## The area-weighted global mean
print(paste('Area-weighted global mean',globalMean(TP[['high']])))
```

```
## [1] "Area-weighted global mean 104.306185243484"
```

```
breaks <- seq(0,500,by=10)
cols <- rep('darkgreen',length(breaks))
cols[breaks < 100] <- 'brown'
hist(rhstats,breaks=breaks,col=cols,main='High records',
     xlab='number or record-breaking seasonal rainfall')
```

High records


```
## Record-lows
#rlstats <- c(TP[['low.djf']],TP[['low.mam']],TP[['low.jja']],TP[['low.son']])
rlstats <- c(TP[['low']])
print(summary(rlstats))
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
## 22.22  83.77   94.03  92.94 102.57 186.34
```

```
## The area-weighted global mean
print(paste('Area-weighted global mean',globalMean(TP[['low']])))
```

```
## [1] "Area-weighted global mean 93.8808191360001"
```

```
cols <- rep('darkgreen',length(breaks))
cols[breaks >= 100] <- 'brown'
hist(rlstats,breaks=breaks,col=cols,main='Low records',
```

```
xlab='number or record-breaking annual rainfall')
```

Low records


```
print(summary(rhstats/rlstats))
```

```
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
## 0.1978 0.9667  1.1429  1.1972  1.3585  5.6667
```

The global statistics for the number of record-breaking events for seasonal rainfall amounts indicate a tendency towards more extreme annual wet rainfall amounts.

3.3.6 Area with high precipitation

```
par(cex.main=0.75)
pgt50 <- subset(
  AreaClimateIndicator(param='precip',FUN='mean',threshold=50,plot=FALSE),it=c(1950,2023))
pgt90 <- subset(
  AreaClimateIndicator(param='precip',FUN='mean',threshold=90,plot=FALSE),it=c(1950,2023))
Aref50 <- mean(subset(pgt50,it=c(1951,1980)))
Aref90 <- mean(subset(pgt90,it=c(1951,1980)))
print(paste('Aref50=',round(Aearth*Aref50),'km^2; Aref90=',round(Aearth*Aref90),'km^2'))
```

```
## [1] "Aref50= 1112354 km^2; Aref90= 206213 km^2"
```

```
pgt50 <- 100*pgt50/Aref50
pgt90 <- 100*pgt90/Aref90
plot(merge(pgt50,pgt90),col=c('black','red'),plot.type='single',ylab='% ',xlab='',
      main='Fractional area of heavy 24-hr precipitation (wrt. 1951-1980)',lwd=2)
grid()
legend(1950,225,c(expression(P > 50*mm/day),expression(p > 90*mm/day)),lty=1,
      col=c('black','red'),lwd=2,bty='n')
```

Fractional area of heavy 24-hr precipitation (wrt. 1951-1980)

The curves representing the area fraction with daily precipitation exceeding the thresholds of 50 mm/day and 90 mm/day show increases, with a stronger relative increase for the higher threshold. These results indicate that extreme daily rainfall is becoming more widespread globally.

3.4 Record-breaking-recurrence statistics from GCMs

Statistics of record-breaking-recurrence can also be derived from global climate models and compared to those from ERA5 to assess the models' ability to reproduce extreme temperatures and rainfall. One approach is to follow a similar approach as in Benestad et al. (2023) using EOFs to compare maps of record-breaking rates for both temperature and precipitation over the same period 1950–2022.

The following chunk performs all the calculations and takes a long time. The results of these calculations are saved in an R binary file, which can then be analysed.

```
fname <- '~/R/records.cmip6ssp245.rda'
path.gcms <- '/home/rasmusb/data/CMIP/CMIP6.monthly/ssp245'
```

```

t0 <- Sys.time()

print('tas:')
if (file.exists(fname)) {
  ## Use pre-computed results
  load (fname)
  finished <- names(gcm.results)
  finished <- finished[grep('.high.t2m.hist',finished)]
  finished <- sub(path.gcms,'',finished)
  finished <- gsub('/','',finished)
  finished <- sub('_1850-2100.nc','',finished)
  finished <- sub('_ssp245_', '.',finished)
  finished <- sub('tas_Amon_', '',finished)
  finished <- sub('.high.t2m.hist','',finished)
  print(finished)
  print(paste(length(finished),'GCM simulation are completed'))
  #if (length(finished)>0) gcms <- gcms[-grep(gcms,finished)]
} else {
  ## Need to do all the calculations from individual members of CMIP6 ensemble
  gcms <- list.files(path=path.gcms,pattern='tas_Amon',full.names = TRUE)
  print(length(gcms))
  gcms <- gcms[grep('_1850-2100.nc',gcms)]
  print(length(gcms))
  ## Need to skip the very high-resolution data due to limited computing capacity (memory)
  datasize <- file.size(gcms)
  keep <- datasize <= 824445068
  gcms <- gcms[keep]
  print(length(gcms))
  gcm.results <- list()
  print(gcms)
  for (gcm in gcms) {
    print(paste('Read>',gcm))
    Z <- retrieve(gcm,it=c(1950,2100))
    gcmname <- sub(path.gcms,'',gcm)
    gcmname <- gsub('/','',gcmname)
    gcmname <- sub('_1850-2100.nc','',gcmname)
    gcmname <- sub('_ssp245_', '.',gcmname)
    gcmname <- sub('tas_Amon_', '',gcmname)
    print(gcmname)
    Z.hist <- subset(Z,it=c(1950,2022))
    high.hist <- percent.records(Z.hist)
    low.hist <- percent.records(-Z.hist)
    ar1.hist <- try(AR1(Z.hist))
    Z.future <- subset(Z,it=c(2025,2100))
    high.future <- percent.records(Z.future)
    low.future <- percent.records(-Z.future)
    ar1.future <- try(AR1(Z.future))
    gcm.results[[paste0(gcmname, '.high.t2m.hist')]] <- high.hist
    gcm.results[[paste0(gcmname, '.low.t2m.hist')]] <- low.hist
    gcm.results[[paste0(gcmname, '.ar1.t2m.hist')]] <- ar1.hist
    gcm.results[[paste0(gcmname, '.high.t2m.future')]] <- high.future
    gcm.results[[paste0(gcmname, '.low.t2m.future')]] <- low.future
    gcm.results[[paste0(gcmname, '.ar1.t2m.future')]] <- ar1.future
  }
}

```

```

    save(gcm.results,file=fname)
    t1 <- Sys.time()
    print(paste('Processing time=',t1 - t0))
  }
}

print('pr:')
gcms <- list.files(path=path.gcms,pattern='pr_Amon',full.names = TRUE)
print(length(gcms))
gcms <- gcms[grep('_1850-2100.nc',gcms)]
print(length(gcms))
datasize <- file.size(gcms)
keep <- datasize <= 824445068
gcms <- gcms[keep]
print(length(gcms))
if (file.exists(fname)) {
  load (fname)
  finished <- names(gcm.results)
  finished <- finished[grep('.high.pr.hist',finished)]
  finished <- sub(path.gcms,'',finished)
  finished <- gsub('/','',finished)
  finished <- sub('_1850-2100.nc','',finished)
  finished <- sub('_ssp245_','.',finished)
  finished <- sub('pr_Amon','',finished)
  finished <- sub('.high.pr.hist','',finished)
  print(finished)
  print(paste(length(finished),'GCM simulation are completed'))
  if (length(finished)>0) gcms <- gcms[-grep(gcms,finished)]
} else gcm.results <- list()
## Check the file size
print(gcms)
for (gcm in gcms) {
  print(paste('Read>',gcm))
  Z <- retrieve(gcm,it=c(1950,2100))
  gcname <- sub(path.gcms,'',gcm)
  gcname <- gsub('/','',gcname)
  gcname <- sub('_1850-2100.nc','',gcname)
  gcname <- sub('_ssp245_','.',gcname)
  gcname <- sub('pr_Amon','',gcname)
  print(gcname)
  Z.hist <- subset(Z,it=c(1950,2022))
  high.hist <- percent.records(Z.hist)
  low.hist <- percent.records(-Z.hist)
  ar1.hist <- AR1(Z.hist)
  Z.future <- subset(Z,it=c(2025,2100))
  high.future <- percent.records(Z.future)
  low.future <- percent.records(-Z.future)
  ar1.future <- AR1(Z.future)
  gcm.results[[paste0(gcname, '.high.pr.hist')]] <- high.hist
  gcm.results[[paste0(gcname, '.low.pr.hist')]] <- low.hist
  gcm.results[[paste0(gcname, '.ar1.pr.hist')]] <- ar1.hist
  gcm.results[[paste0(gcname, '.high.pr.future')]] <- high.future
  gcm.results[[paste0(gcname, '.low.pr.future')]] <- low.future

```

```

gcm.results[[paste0(gcmname, '.ar1.pr.future')]] <- ar1.future
save(gcm.results, file=fname)
t1 <- Sys.time()
print(paste('Processing time=', t1 - t0))
}

```

A summary of the GCM runs are provided by

```

fname <- '~/R/records.cmip6ssp245.rda'
load(fname)
hist.t2m <- table(sub('\\.*', '', names(gcm.results)[grep('high.t2m.hist', names(gcm.results))]))
print(hist.t2m)

```

```

##
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##              5              40              1              38
##      CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##              1              3              3              1
##      CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##              1              1              6              10
##      EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
##              3              1              1              3
##      GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H      HadGEM3-GC31-LL      INM-CM4-8
##              24              5              5              1
##      INM-CM5-0      IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G      KIOST-ESM
##              1              11              3              1
##      MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6      MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##              1              30              50              30
##      MRI-ESM2-0      NESM3      NorESM2-LM      NorESM2-MM
##              5              2              3              2
##      TaiESM1      UKESM1-0-LL
##              1              14

```

```

nruns <- length(grep('high.t2m.hist', names(gcm.results)))
print(paste(nruns, 'runs with', length(rownames(hist.t2m)), 'different GCMs for historical TAS'))

```

```
## [1] "307 runs with 34 different GCMs for historical TAS"
```

```

future.t2m <- table(sub('\\.*', '', names(gcm.results)[grep('high.t2m.future', names(gcm.results))]))
print(future.t2m)

```

```

##
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##              5              40              1              38
##      CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##              1              3              3              1
##      CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##              1              1              6              10
##      EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
##              3              1              1              3
##      GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H      HadGEM3-GC31-LL      INM-CM4-8
##              24              5              5              1
##      INM-CM5-0      IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G      KIOST-ESM
##              1              11              3              1
##      MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6      MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##              1              30              50              30

```

```
##      MRI-ESM2-0          NESM3      NorESM2-LM      NorESM2-MM
##          5              2          3              2
##      TaiESM1      UKESM1-0-LL
##          1              14
```

```
nruns <- length(grep('high.t2m.future',names(gcm.results)))
print(paste(nruns,'runs with',length(rownames(hist.t2m)),'different GCMs for future TAS'))
```

```
## [1] "307 runs with 34 different GCMs for future TAS"
```

```
hist.pr <- table(sub('\\.*',',',names(gcm.results)[grep('high.pr.hist',names(gcm.results))]))
print(hist.pr)
```

```
##
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##          5              40              1              38
##      CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##          3              3              3              1
##      CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##          1              1              6              10
##      EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
##          3              1              2              3
##      GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H      HadGEM3-GC31-LL      INM-CM4-8
##          24              5              5              1
##      INM-CM5-0      IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G      KIOST-ESM
##          1              11              3              1
##      MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6      MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##          1              30              50              30
##      MRI-ESM2-0          NESM3      NorESM2-LM      NorESM2-MM
##          5              2          3              2
##      TaiESM1      UKESM1-0-LL
##          1              14
```

```
nruns <- length(grep('high.pr.hist',names(gcm.results)))
print(paste(nruns,'runs with',length(rownames(hist.pr)),'different GCMs for historical PR'))
```

```
## [1] "310 runs with 34 different GCMs for historical PR"
```

```
future.pr <- table(sub('\\.*',',',names(gcm.results)[grep('high.pr.future',names(gcm.results))]))
print(future.pr)
```

```
##
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##          5              40              1              38
##      CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##          3              3              3              1
##      CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##          1              1              6              10
##      EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
##          3              1              2              3
##      GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H      HadGEM3-GC31-LL      INM-CM4-8
##          24              5              5              1
##      INM-CM5-0      IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G      KIOST-ESM
##          1              11              3              1
##      MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6      MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##          1              30              50              30
##      MRI-ESM2-0          NESM3      NorESM2-LM      NorESM2-MM
```

```
##           5           2           3           2
##      TaiESM1      UKESM1-0-LL
##           1           14

nrns <- length(grep('high.pr.future',names(gcm.results)))
print(paste(nrns,'runs with',length(rownames(hist.pr)), 'different GCMs for future PR'))

## [1] "310 runs with 34 different GCMs for future PR"
```

3.5 Simulated annual mean temperature (CMIP6)

A map of the ensemble mean high temperature record-breaking-recurrence ζ provides a smoother picture than any single model simulation of ERA5.

```
high.T2m.ERA5.record.stats <- regrid(high.T2m.ERA5.record.stats,is=t2m)
gcm.results[['ERA5']] <- high.T2m.ERA5.record.stats
print(table(unlist(
  lapply(strsplit(names(gcm.results[grep('high.t2m.hist',names(gcm.results))]),
    split=".",fixed=TRUE),function(x) x[1]))))
```

```
##
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##           5           40           1           38
##      CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##           1           3           3           1
##      CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##           1           1           6           10
##      EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
##           3           1           1           3
##      GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H      HadGEM3-GC31-LL      INM-CM4-8
##           24           5           5           1
##      INM-CM5-0      IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G      KIOST-ESM
##           1           11           3           1
##      MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6      MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##           1           30           50           30
##      MRI-ESM2-0      NESM3      NorESM2-LM      NorESM2-MM
##           5           2           3           2
##      TaiESM1      UKESM1-0-LL
##           1           14
```

```
y <- list2field(gcm.results,it='high.t2m.hist')
```

```
## Warning in matrix(rep(NA, n * nxy), n + 1, nxy): data length [3227184] is not a
## sub-multiple or multiple of the number of rows [308]
```

```
m1 <- map(subset(y,it=2:307),colbar=list(pal='t2m.ipcc'),
  projection="+proj=robin",
  main='Historical annual mean temperature record-breaking recurrences')
```

Historical annual mean temperature record-breaking recurrences


```
ceof <- EOF(y,anomaly=FALSE)
print(100*attr(ceof,'eigenvalues')^2/attr(ceof,'tot.var'))

## [1] 97.87943408 0.22057924 0.14289890 0.09646264 0.07333382 0.06905126
## [7] 0.05571114 0.04663426 0.04177767 0.03996920 0.03452155 0.03150541
## [13] 0.03109390 0.02769546 0.02681163 0.02555255 0.02415998 0.02117289
## [19] 0.02060817 0.02025801

map(ceof,main='EOF#1 of ERA5 and simulated record-breaking recurrences',
    projection="+proj=robin")
```

EOF#1 of ERA5 and simulated record-breaking recurrences


```
par(new=FALSE)  
plot(ceof, what="var")
```

20 leading EOFs: 98.9 % of variance


```
## Identify model
mid <- c('ERA5',unlist(
  lapply(strsplit(attr(ceof, 'ID'),split='.',fixed=TRUE),function(x) x[1])))
print(table(mid))
```

```
## mid
##      ACCESS-CM2  ACCESS-ESM1-5  BCC-CSM2-MR  CanESM5
##           5           40           1           38
##  CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2  CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##           1           3           3           1
##  CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2  CNRM-CM6-1  CNRM-ESM2-1
##           1           1           6           10
##  EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      ERA5  FGOALS-f3-L  FGOALS-g3
##           3           1           1           1
##  FIO-ESM-2-0  GISS-E2-1-G  GISS-E2-1-H  HadGEM3-GC31-LL
##           3           24           5           5
##  INM-CM4-8  INM-CM5-0  IPSL-CM6A-LR  KACE-1-0-G
##           1           1           11           3
##  KIOST-ESM  MCM-UA-1-0  MIROC-ES2L  MIROC6
```

```
##          1          1          30          50
##  MPI-ESM1-2-LR      MRI-ESM2-0      NESM3      NorESM2-LM
##          30          5          2          3
##      NorESM2-MM      TaiESM1      UKESM1-0-LL
##          2          1          14
```

```
nm <- length(rownames(table(mid)))
col <- rep('grey',length(index(ceof)))
col[grep('ACCESS',mid)] <- 'blue'
col[grep('CanESM5',mid)] <- "brown"
col[grep('GISS-E2',mid)] <- "purple"
col[grep('MIROC-ES2L',mid)] <- "darkgreen"
col[grep('MPI-ESM1-2-LR',mid)] <- "orange"
col[grep('UKESM1-0-LL',mid)] <- "cyan"
plot(coredata(ceof)[,1],main='PC#1',col=col,ylab='weight',xlab='member')
points(1,ceof[1,1],pch=19,col='red',cex=1.5)
grid()
legend(250,0.07,
       c('ACCESS','CanESM5','GISS-E2','MIROC-ES2L','MPI-ESM1','UKESM1','others'),
       col = c('blue','brown','purple','darkgreen','orange','cyan','grey'),
       pch=21,bty='n',cex=0.75)
```



```
## Second mode:
map(ceof, ip=2, main='EOF#2 of ERA5 and simulated record-breaking recurrences',
    projection="+proj=robin")
```

EOF#2 of ERA5 and simulated record-breaking recurrences


```
plot(coredata(ceof)[,2],main='PC#2',col=col,ylab='weight',xlab='member')  
points(1,ceof[1,2],pch=19,col='red',cex=1.5)  
grid()
```


The results indicate a latitude band of higher ζ in the tropics and lower at higher latitudes, but all values are greater than those expected from an iid process (100).

The common-EOF-based evaluation indicates that almost all the variance is in the leading mode (98%), which has the strongest weights over tropical oceans. A comparison between ERA5 and the CMIP6 results suggests that the model spread encompasses the observations. One model (CanESM5) tends to be shifted away from the others, but there is also a spread between different runs with one individual model (respective colours).

The second common EOFs represents ‘noise’ and only accounts for 0.2% of the variance, showing a pattern of finer details that differ between the models’ reproduction of ζ in the tropics. For mode #2, the spread within one specific model is similar to the spread between models.

```
y <- list2field(gcm.results,it='high.t2m.future')
```

```
## Warning in matrix(rep(NA, n * nxy), n + 1, nxy): data length [3227184] is not a
## sub-multiple or multiple of the number of rows [308]
```

```
y <- subset(y,it=2:307)
m2 <- map(y,colbar=list(pal='t2m.ipcc'),projection="+proj=robin",
          main='Projected future annual mean temperature record-breaking recurrences')
```

Projected future annual mean temperature record-breaking recurrences

The record-breaking high annual mean temperature simulated for the future (306 CMIP6 SSP245 runs) indicates a continuation of trends seen in the past, but with a strengthening of the high ζ for tropical maritime regions. One interpretation is that tropical marine heatwaves may become more intense, widespread and longer lasting.

We can subsample the multi-model ensemble presented above and extract only one member for each GCM to see if the results for the large ensemble is strongly influenced by many simulations with a few of the GCMs.

```
id <- attr(y, 'ID')
r1i1p1f1 <- grep('r1i1p1f1', id)
y1 <- subset(y, it=r1i1p1f1) ## ensemble with only one run per GCM
print(attr(y1, 'ID'))
```

```
## [1] "ACCESS-CM2.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [2] "ACCESS-CM2.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [3] "ACCESS-CM2.r3i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [4] "ACCESS-CM2.r4i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [5] "ACCESS-CM2.r5i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [6] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r10i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [7] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r11i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [8] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r12i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
```

[9] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r13i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[10] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r14i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[11] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r15i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[12] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r16i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[13] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r17i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[14] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r18i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[15] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r19i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[16] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[17] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r20i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[18] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r21i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[19] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r22i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[20] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r23i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[21] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r24i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[22] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r25i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[23] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r26i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[24] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r27i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[25] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r28i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[26] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r29i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[27] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[28] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r30i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[29] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r31i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[30] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r32i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[31] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r33i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[32] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r34i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[33] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r35i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[34] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r36i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[35] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r37i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[36] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r38i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[37] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r39i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[38] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r3i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[39] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r40i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[40] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r4i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[41] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r5i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[42] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r6i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[43] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r7i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[44] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r8i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[45] "ACCESS-ESM1-5.r9i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[46] "BCC-CSM2-MR.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[47] "CanESM5.r10i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[48] "CanESM5.r10i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
[49] "CanESM5.r11i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[50] "CanESM5.r11i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
[51] "CanESM5.r12i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[52] "CanESM5.r12i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
[53] "CanESM5.r13i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[54] "CanESM5.r13i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
[55] "CanESM5.r14i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[56] "CanESM5.r14i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
[57] "CanESM5.r15i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[58] "CanESM5.r15i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
[59] "CanESM5.r16i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[60] "CanESM5.r16i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
[61] "CanESM5.r17i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[62] "CanESM5.r17i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"

```

## [63] "CanESM5.r18i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [64] "CanESM5.r18i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
## [65] "CanESM5.r19i1p1f1_gn.high.t2m.future"
## [66] "CanESM5.r19i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
## [67] "CanESM5.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [68] "CanESM5.r1i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
## [69] "CanESM5.r20i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [70] "CanESM5.r20i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
## [71] "CanESM5.r21i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
## [72] "CanESM5.r22i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [73] "CanESM5.r22i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
## [74] "CanESM5.r23i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [75] "CanESM5.r23i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
## [76] "CanESM5.r24i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [77] "CanESM5.r24i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
## [78] "CanESM5.r25i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
## [79] "CanESM5.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [80] "CanESM5.r4i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [81] "CanESM5.r5i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [82] "CanESM5.r5i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
## [83] "CanESM5.r8i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [84] "CanESM5.r8i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
## [85] "CanESM5-CanOE.r1i1p2f1.high.t2m.future"
## [86] "CESM2.r10i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [87] "CESM2.r11i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [88] "CESM2.r4i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [89] "CESM2-WACCM.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [90] "CESM2-WACCM.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [91] "CESM2-WACCM.r3i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [92] "CIesm.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [93] "CMCC-CM2-SR5.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [94] "CMCC-ESM2.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [95] "CNRM-CM6-1.r1i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [96] "CNRM-CM6-1.r2i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [97] "CNRM-CM6-1.r3i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [98] "CNRM-CM6-1.r4i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [99] "CNRM-CM6-1.r5i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [100] "CNRM-CM6-1.r6i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [101] "CNRM-ESM2-1.r10i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [102] "CNRM-ESM2-1.r1i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [103] "CNRM-ESM2-1.r2i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [104] "CNRM-ESM2-1.r3i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [105] "CNRM-ESM2-1.r4i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [106] "CNRM-ESM2-1.r5i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [107] "CNRM-ESM2-1.r6i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [108] "CNRM-ESM2-1.r7i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [109] "CNRM-ESM2-1.r8i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [110] "CNRM-ESM2-1.r9i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [111] "EC-Earth3-Veg-LR.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [112] "EC-Earth3-Veg-LR.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [113] "EC-Earth3-Veg-LR.r3i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [114] "FGOALS-f3-L.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [115] "FGOALS-g3.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [116] "FIO-ESM-2-0.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"

```

[117] "FIO-ESM-2-0.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[118] "FIO-ESM-2-0.r3i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[119] "GISS-E2-1-G.r10i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[120] "GISS-E2-1-G.r10i1p5f1.high.t2m.future"
[121] "GISS-E2-1-G.r1i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[122] "GISS-E2-1-G.r1i1p3f1.high.t2m.future"
[123] "GISS-E2-1-G.r1i1p5f1.high.t2m.future"
[124] "GISS-E2-1-G.r2i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[125] "GISS-E2-1-G.r2i1p3f1.high.t2m.future"
[126] "GISS-E2-1-G.r2i1p5f1.high.t2m.future"
[127] "GISS-E2-1-G.r3i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[128] "GISS-E2-1-G.r3i1p3f1.high.t2m.future"
[129] "GISS-E2-1-G.r3i1p5f1.high.t2m.future"
[130] "GISS-E2-1-G.r4i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[131] "GISS-E2-1-G.r4i1p3f1.high.t2m.future"
[132] "GISS-E2-1-G.r4i1p5f1.high.t2m.future"
[133] "GISS-E2-1-G.r5i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[134] "GISS-E2-1-G.r5i1p3f1.high.t2m.future"
[135] "GISS-E2-1-G.r6i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[136] "GISS-E2-1-G.r6i1p5f1.high.t2m.future"
[137] "GISS-E2-1-G.r7i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[138] "GISS-E2-1-G.r7i1p5f1.high.t2m.future"
[139] "GISS-E2-1-G.r8i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[140] "GISS-E2-1-G.r8i1p5f1.high.t2m.future"
[141] "GISS-E2-1-G.r9i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[142] "GISS-E2-1-G.r9i1p5f1.high.t2m.future"
[143] "GISS-E2-1-H.r1i1p3f1.high.t2m.future"
[144] "GISS-E2-1-H.r2i1p3f1.high.t2m.future"
[145] "GISS-E2-1-H.r3i1p3f1.high.t2m.future"
[146] "GISS-E2-1-H.r4i1p3f1.high.t2m.future"
[147] "GISS-E2-1-H.r5i1p3f1.high.t2m.future"
[148] "HadGEM3-GC31-LL.r1i1p1f3.high.t2m.future"
[149] "HadGEM3-GC31-LL.r2i1p1f3.high.t2m.future"
[150] "HadGEM3-GC31-LL.r3i1p1f3.high.t2m.future"
[151] "HadGEM3-GC31-LL.r4i1p1f3.high.t2m.future"
[152] "HadGEM3-GC31-LL.r5i1p1f3.high.t2m.future"
[153] "INM-CM4-8.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[154] "INM-CM5-0.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[155] "IPSL-CM6A-LR.r10i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[156] "IPSL-CM6A-LR.r11i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[157] "IPSL-CM6A-LR.r14i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[158] "IPSL-CM6A-LR.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[159] "IPSL-CM6A-LR.r22i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[160] "IPSL-CM6A-LR.r25i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[161] "IPSL-CM6A-LR.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[162] "IPSL-CM6A-LR.r3i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[163] "IPSL-CM6A-LR.r4i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[164] "IPSL-CM6A-LR.r5i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[165] "IPSL-CM6A-LR.r6i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[166] "KACE-1-0-G.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[167] "KACE-1-0-G.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[168] "KACE-1-0-G.r3i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[169] "KIOST-ESM.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[170] "MCM-UA-1-0.r1i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"

[171] "MIROC-ES2L.r10i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[172] "MIROC-ES2L.r11i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[173] "MIROC-ES2L.r12i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[174] "MIROC-ES2L.r13i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[175] "MIROC-ES2L.r14i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[176] "MIROC-ES2L.r15i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[177] "MIROC-ES2L.r16i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[178] "MIROC-ES2L.r17i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[179] "MIROC-ES2L.r18i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[180] "MIROC-ES2L.r19i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[181] "MIROC-ES2L.r1i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[182] "MIROC-ES2L.r20i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[183] "MIROC-ES2L.r21i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[184] "MIROC-ES2L.r22i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[185] "MIROC-ES2L.r23i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[186] "MIROC-ES2L.r24i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[187] "MIROC-ES2L.r25i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[188] "MIROC-ES2L.r26i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[189] "MIROC-ES2L.r27i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[190] "MIROC-ES2L.r28i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[191] "MIROC-ES2L.r29i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[192] "MIROC-ES2L.r2i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[193] "MIROC-ES2L.r30i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[194] "MIROC-ES2L.r3i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[195] "MIROC-ES2L.r4i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[196] "MIROC-ES2L.r5i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[197] "MIROC-ES2L.r6i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[198] "MIROC-ES2L.r7i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[199] "MIROC-ES2L.r8i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[200] "MIROC-ES2L.r9i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
[201] "MIROC6.r10i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[202] "MIROC6.r11i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[203] "MIROC6.r12i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[204] "MIROC6.r13i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[205] "MIROC6.r14i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[206] "MIROC6.r15i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[207] "MIROC6.r16i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[208] "MIROC6.r17i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[209] "MIROC6.r18i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[210] "MIROC6.r19i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[211] "MIROC6.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[212] "MIROC6.r20i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[213] "MIROC6.r21i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[214] "MIROC6.r22i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[215] "MIROC6.r23i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[216] "MIROC6.r24i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[217] "MIROC6.r25i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[218] "MIROC6.r26i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[219] "MIROC6.r27i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[220] "MIROC6.r28i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[221] "MIROC6.r29i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[222] "MIROC6.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[223] "MIROC6.r30i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[224] "MIROC6.r3i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"

[225] "MIROC6.r32i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[226] "MIROC6.r33i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[227] "MIROC6.r34i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[228] "MIROC6.r35i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[229] "MIROC6.r36i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[230] "MIROC6.r37i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[231] "MIROC6.r38i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[232] "MIROC6.r39i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[233] "MIROC6.r3i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[234] "MIROC6.r40i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[235] "MIROC6.r41i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[236] "MIROC6.r42i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[237] "MIROC6.r43i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[238] "MIROC6.r44i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[239] "MIROC6.r45i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[240] "MIROC6.r46i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[241] "MIROC6.r47i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[242] "MIROC6.r48i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[243] "MIROC6.r49i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[244] "MIROC6.r4i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[245] "MIROC6.r50i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[246] "MIROC6.r5i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[247] "MIROC6.r6i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[248] "MIROC6.r7i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[249] "MIROC6.r8i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[250] "MIROC6.r9i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[251] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r10i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[252] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r11i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[253] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r12i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[254] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r13i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[255] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r14i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[256] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r15i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[257] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r16i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[258] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r17i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[259] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r18i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[260] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r19i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[261] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[262] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r20i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[263] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r21i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[264] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r22i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[265] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r23i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[266] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r24i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[267] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r25i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[268] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r26i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[269] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r27i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[270] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r28i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[271] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r29i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[272] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[273] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r30i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[274] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r3i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[275] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r4i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[276] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r5i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[277] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r6i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
[278] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r7i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"

```

## [279] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r8i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [280] "MPI-ESM1-2-LR.r9i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [281] "MRI-ESM2-0.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [282] "MRI-ESM2-0.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [283] "MRI-ESM2-0.r3i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [284] "MRI-ESM2-0.r4i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [285] "MRI-ESM2-0.r5i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [286] "NESM3.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [287] "NESM3.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [288] "NorESM2-LM.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [289] "NorESM2-LM.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [290] "NorESM2-LM.r3i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [291] "NorESM2-MM.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [292] "NorESM2-MM.r2i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [293] "TaiESM1.r1i1p1f1.high.t2m.future"
## [294] "UKESM1-0-LL.r10i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [295] "UKESM1-0-LL.r11i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [296] "UKESM1-0-LL.r12i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [297] "UKESM1-0-LL.r13i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [298] "UKESM1-0-LL.r16i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [299] "UKESM1-0-LL.r17i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [300] "UKESM1-0-LL.r18i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [301] "UKESM1-0-LL.r19i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [302] "UKESM1-0-LL.r1i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [303] "UKESM1-0-LL.r2i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [304] "UKESM1-0-LL.r3i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [305] "UKESM1-0-LL.r4i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [306] "UKESM1-0-LL.r8i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"
## [307] "UKESM1-0-LL.r9i1p1f2.high.t2m.future"

```

```

m2s <- map(y1,colbar=list(pal='t2m.ipcc'),projection="+proj=robin",
           main=paste('Projected future recurrence rate from reduced ensemble; n=',
                      length(r1i1p1f1)))

```

Projected future recurrence rate from reduced ensemble; n= 24

The ensemble mean map for the 406-member sample with several GCMs run multiple times and the 24-member sample with only one run for each GCM (r1i1p1f1) were similar, and the results were not sensitive to the choice of including multiple or only single runs for different GCMs. Here only the r1i1p1f1 are shown, but some GCMs did not have this run ID.

A map of the differences between ζ estimated for the past and future highlights projected changes.

```
map(m2 - m1, main='Simulated change in record-high annual mean TAS recurrences',  
    colbar=list(breaks=seq(-100,100,by=20),pal='t2m.ipcc'),projection="+proj=robin")
```

Simulated change in record-high annual mean TAS recurrences

The simulations suggest a stronger increase in ζ in the Arctic in the future, more similar to the geographical patterns of current temperature trends.

3.5.1 Maps of record-low annual mean temperature.

```
low.T2m.ERA5.record.stats <- regrid(low.T2m.ERA5.record.stats,is=t2m)
gcm.results[['ERA5']] <- low.T2m.ERA5.record.stats
print(table(unlist(
  lapply(strsplit(names(gcm.results[grep('low.t2m.hist',names(gcm.results))]),
    split=".",fixed=TRUE),function(x) x[1]))))
```

```
##
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##              5              40              1              38
##      CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##              1              3              3              1
##      CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##              1              1              6              10
```

```

## EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
##           3           1           1           3
##   GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H  HadGEM3-GC31-LL  INM-CM4-8
##           24           5           5           1
##   INM-CM5-0      IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G      KIOST-ESM
##           1           11           3           1
##   MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6      MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##           1           30           50           30
##   MRI-ESM2-0      NESM3      NorESM2-LM      NorESM2-MM
##           5           2           3           2
##   TaiESM1      UKESM1-0-LL
##           1           14

```

```
y <- list2field(gcm.results,it='low.t2m.hist')
```

```
## Warning in matrix(rep(NA, n * nxy), n + 1, nxy): data length [3227184] is not a
## sub-multiple or multiple of the number of rows [308]
```

```
m1 <- map(subset(y,it=2:307),colbar=list(pal='t2m',rev=TRUE),projection="+proj=robin",
          main='Historical annual mean temperature low record-breaking recurrences')
```

historical annual mean temperature low record-breaking recurrences


```
ceof <- EOF(y,anomaly=FALSE)
print(100*attr(ceof,'eigenvalues')^2/attr(ceof,'tot.var'))

## [1] 97.48824498 0.28450177 0.13466929 0.08250256 0.07203157 0.06169829
## [7] 0.05739170 0.04940824 0.04794376 0.04213751 0.04047907 0.03941539
## [13] 0.03704374 0.03489565 0.03396124 0.03273810 0.03097638 0.02867233
## [19] 0.02707369 0.02606397

map(ceof,main='EOF#1 of ERA5 and simulated low record-breaking recurrences',
    projection="+proj=robin")
```

EOF#1 of ERA5 and simulated low record-breaking recurrences


```
par(new=FALSE)  
plot(ceof, what="var")
```

20 leading EOFs: 98.7 % of variance


```
mid <- unlist(lapply(strsplit(attr(ceof, 'ID'), split='.', fixed=TRUE), function(x) x[1]))
print(table(mid))
```

```
## mid
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##           5           40           1           38
##      CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##           1           3           3           1
##      CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##           1           1           6           10
##      EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
##           3           1           1           3
##      GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H      HadGEM3-GC31-LL      INM-CM4-8
##          24           5           5           1
##      INM-CM5-0      IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G      KIOST-ESM
##           1           11           3           1
##      MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6      MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##           1           30           50           30
##      MRI-ESM2-0      NESM3      NorESM2-LM      NorESM2-MM
```

```
##          5          2          3          2
##      TaiESM1      UKESM1-0-LL
##          1          14
```

```
nm <- length(rownames(table(mid)))
col <- rep('grey',length(index(ceof)))
col[grep('ACCESS',mid)] <- 'blue'
col[grep('CanESM5',mid)] <- "brown"
col[grep('GISS-E2',mid)] <- "purple"
col[grep('MIROC-ES2L',mid)] <- "darkgreen"
col[grep('MPI-ESM1-2-LR',mid)] <- "orange"
col[grep('UKESM1-0-LL',mid)] <- "cyan"
plot(coredata(ceof)[,1],main='PC#1',col=col)
points(1,ceof[1,1],pch=19,col='red',cex=1.5)
grid()
```



```
## Second mode:
map(ceof,ip=2,main='EOF#2 of ERA5 and simulated low record-breaking recurrences',
    projection="+proj=robin")
```

EOF#2 of ERA5 and simulated low record-breaking recurrences


```
plot(coredata(ceof)[,2],main='PC#2',col=col)
points(1,ceof[1,2],pch=19,col='red',cex=1.5)
grid()
```


The common EOF evaluation of ζ for record-low annual mean temperature indicates that most of the information is embedded in the leading mode (variance accounts for 97%) and that the scatter of results from GCMs is consistent with ζ from ERA5. The leading mode has stronger weights over the mid-latitude oceans whereas the second mode (0.3% variance) reflects contrasts between tropical and mid-latitude oceans. The spread within individual models is greater than the spread between different models.

The maps of low temperature record-breaking recurrences provide a similar picture to the record highs.

```
y <- list2field(gcm.results,it='low.t2m.future')

## Warning in matrix(rep(NA, n * nxy), n + 1, nxy): data length [3227184] is not a
## sub-multiple or multiple of the number of rows [308]

y <- subset(y,it=2:307)
m2 <- map(y,colbar=list(pal='t2m.ipcc'),projection="+proj=robin",
          main='Projected future annual mean TAS low record-breaking recurrences')
```

Projected future annual mean TAS low record-breaking recurrences

Maps of differences.

```
map(m2 - m1,colbar=list(rev=TRUE),projection="+proj=robin",  
    main='Simulated change in record-low annual mean TAS recurrences')
```

Simulated change in record-low annual mean TAS recurrences

3.5.2 Maps of AR1.

```
## Reduce the spatial dimensions of AR1 map to cope with memory limitations
ar1.t2m <- regrid(ar1.t2m,is=high.T2m.ERA5.record.stats)
## Repeat as above
gcm.results[['ERA5']] <- ar1.t2m
print(table(unlist(
  lapply(strsplit(names(gcm.results[grep('ar1.t2m.hist',names(gcm.results))]),
    split=".",fixed=TRUE),function(x) x[1]))))
```

```
##
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##          5          40          1          38
##      CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##          1          3          3          1
##      CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##          1          1          6          10
##      EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
```

```
##          3          1          1          3
## GISS-E2-1-G GISS-E2-1-H HadGEM3-GC31-LL INM-CM4-8
##          24          5          5          1
## INM-CM5-0 IPSL-CM6A-LR KACE-1-0-G KIOST-ESM
##          1          11          3          1
## MCM-UA-1-0 MIROC-ES2L MIROC6 MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##          1          30          50          30
## MRI-ESM2-0 NESM3 NorESM2-LM NorESM2-MM
##          5          2          3          2
## TaiESM1 UKESM1-0-LL
##          1          14
```

```
y <- list2field(gcm.results,it='ar1.t2m.hist')
```

```
## Warning in matrix(rep(NA, n * nxy), n + 1, nxy): data length [3227184] is not a
## sub-multiple or multiple of the number of rows [308]
```

```
m1 <- map(subset(y,it=2:307),colbar=list(pal='t2m'),projection="+proj=robin",
          main='Historical annual mean temperature AR1')
```

Historical annual mean temperature AR1


```

ceof <- EOF(y,anomaly=FALSE)
print(100*attr(ceof,'eigenvalues')^2/attr(ceof,'tot.var'))

## [1] 89.77439543 1.45073175 1.20493081 0.97538806 0.71605650 0.45994226
## [7] 0.31632641 0.27493253 0.25339973 0.20499376 0.19182297 0.15240451
## [13] 0.14497664 0.13223965 0.12388450 0.10604125 0.10105793 0.09728002
## [19] 0.09386891 0.07984511

map(ceof,main='EOF#1 of ERA5 and simulated AR1',projection="+proj=robin")

```

EOF#1 of ERA5 and simulated AR1


```

par(new=FALSE)
plot(ceof,what="var")

```

20 leading EOFs: 96.9 % of variance


```
mid <- unlist(
  lapply(strsplit(attr(ceof, 'ID'), split='.', fixed=TRUE), function(x) x[1]))
print(table(mid))
```

```
## mid
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##           5           40           1           38
##      CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##           1           3           3           1
##      CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##           1           1           6           10
##      EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
##           3           1           1           3
##      GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H      HadGEM3-GC31-LL      INM-CM4-8
##          24           5           5           1
##      INM-CM5-0      IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G      KIOST-ESM
##           1           11           3           1
##      MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6      MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##           1           30           50           30
```

##	MRI-ESM2-0	NESM3	NorESM2-LM	NorESM2-MM
##	5	2	3	2
##	TaiESM1	UKESM1-0-LL		
##	1	14		

```

nm <- length(rownames(table(mid)))
col <- rep('grey',length(index(ceof)))
col[grep('ACCESS',mid)] <- 'blue'
col[grep('CanESM5',mid)] <- "brown"
col[grep('GISS-E2',mid)] <- "purple"
col[grep('MIROC-ES2L',mid)] <- "darkgreen"
col[grep('MPI-ESM1-2-LR',mid)] <- "orange"
col[grep('UKESM1-0-LL',mid)] <- "cyan"
plot(coredata(ceof)[,1],main='PC#1',col=col)
points(1,ceof[1,1],pch=19,col='red',cex=1.5)
grid()
legend(250,0.1,
      c('ACCESS','CanESM5','GISS-E2','MIROC-ES2L','MPI-ESM1','UKESM1','others'),
      col = c('blue','brown','purple','darkgreen','orange','cyan','grey'),
      pch=21,bty='n',cex=0.75)

```



```
## Second mode:
map(ceof, ip=2, main='EOF#2 of ERA5 and simulated AR1', projection="+proj=robin")
```

EOF#2 of ERA5 and simulated AR1


```
plot(coredata(ceof)[,2],main='PC#2',col=col)
points(1,ceof[1,2],pch=19,col='red',cex=1.5)
grid()
```


The evaluation of AR1 based on common EOFs suggests that most models reproduce the highest AR1 over the tropical oceans. The leading mode dominates (90% of the variance) whereas the second mode plays a smaller role (1.4%). The scatter of the weights between simulations with one model is of similar magnitude to that between models (represented with different colours) and ERA5.

Plot maps of simulated future annual mean temperature AR1

```
y <- list2field(gcm.results,it='ar1.t2m.future')
```

```
## Warning in matrix(rep(NA, n * nxy), n + 1, nxy): data length [3227184] is not a
## sub-multiple or multiple of the number of rows [308]
```

```
y <- subset(y,it=2:307)
m2 <- map(y,colbar=list(pal='t2m'),main='Projected future annual AR1',
         projection="+proj=robin")
```

Projected future annual AR1

The map of differences below indicates increases in AR1 over the Arctic ocean which may be associated with the disappearance of sea-ice.

```
map(m2 - m1,main='Simulated change in record-high annual AR1',projection="+proj=robin")
```

Simulated change in record-high annual AR1

3.6 Simulated annual rainfall/precipitation (CMIP6)

```
## Reduce the spatial dimensions of AR1 map to cope with memory limitations
high.Tp.ERA5.record.stats <- TP[['high']]
high.Tp.ERA5.record.stats <- regrid(
  high.Tp.ERA5.record.stats, is=high.T2m.ERA5.record.stats)
gcm.results[['ERA5']] <- high.Tp.ERA5.record.stats
print(table(unlist(
  lapply(strsplit(names(gcm.results[grep('high.pr.hist', names(gcm.results))]),
    split=".", fixed=TRUE), function(x) x[1]))))
```

```
##
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##          5          40          1          38
##  CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##          3          3          3          1
##  CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##          1          1          6          10
```

```

## EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
##           3           1           2           3
##      GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H      HadGEM3-GC31-LL      INM-CM4-8
##           24           5           5           1
##      INM-CM5-0      IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G      KIOST-ESM
##           1           11           3           1
##      MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6      MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##           1           30           50           30
##      MRI-ESM2-0      NESM3      NorESM2-LM      NorESM2-MM
##           5           2           3           2
##      TaiESM1      UKESM1-0-LL
##           1           14

```

```
y <- list2field(gcm.results,it='high.pr.hist')
```

```
## Warning in matrix(rep(NA, n * nxy), n + 1, nxy): data length [3258720] is not a
## sub-multiple or multiple of the number of rows [311]
```

```
m1 <- map(subset(y,it=2:307),colbar=list(pal='precip.ipcc'),projection="+proj=robin",
          main='Historical annual rainfall record-breaking recurrences')
```

Historical annual rainfall record-breaking recurrences


```
ceof <- EOF(y,anomaly=FALSE)
print(100*attr(ceof,'eigenvalues')^2/attr(ceof,'tot.var'))

## [1] 98.998714957 0.044131789 0.025279750 0.018960300 0.015190751
## [6] 0.013848987 0.012659824 0.012030206 0.011243182 0.010602138
## [11] 0.009276198 0.009218728 0.008611271 0.008523397 0.008148054
## [16] 0.007669284 0.007641867 0.007483527 0.007169221 0.006991759

map(ceof,projection="+proj=robin",
    main='EOF#1 of ERA5 and simulated record-breaking annual rainfall recurrences')
```

#1 of ERA5 and simulated record-breaking annual rainfall recurrences


```
par(new=FALSE)  
plot(coef, what="var")
```

20 leading EOFs: 99.2 % of variance


```
## Identify model
mid <- c('ERA5',unlist(
  lapply(strsplit(attr(ceof,'ID'),split='.',fixed=TRUE),function(x) x[1])))
print(table(mid))
```

```
## mid
##      ACCESS-CM2  ACCESS-ESM1-5  BCC-CSM2-MR  CanESM5
##           5           40           1           38
##  CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##           3           3           3           1
##  CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##           1           1           6           10
## EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      ERA5      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3
##           3           1           1           2
##  FIO-ESM-2-0      GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H  HadGEM3-GC31-LL
##           3           24           5           5
##  INM-CM4-8      INM-CM5-0  IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G
##           1           1           11           3
##  KIOST-ESM      MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6
```

```
##          1          1          30          50
##  MPI-ESM1-2-LR      MRI-ESM2-0      NESM3      NorESM2-LM
##          30          5          2          3
##      NorESM2-MM      TaiESM1      UKESM1-0-LL
##          2          1          14
```

```
nm <- length(rownames(table(mid)))
col <- rep('grey',length(index(ceof)))
col[grep('ACCESS',mid)] <- 'blue'
col[grep('CanESM5',mid)] <- "brown"
col[grep('GISS-E2',mid)] <- "purple"
col[grep('MIROC-ES2L',mid)] <- "darkgreen"
col[grep('MPI-ESM1-2-LR',mid)] <- "orange"
col[grep('UKESM1-0-LL',mid)] <- "cyan"
plot(coredata(ceof)[,1],main='PC#1',col=col)
points(1,ceof[1,1],pch=19,col='red',cex=1.5)
grid()
legend(250,0.059,
      c('ACCESS','CanESM5','GISS-E2','MIROC-ES2L','MPI-ESM1','UKESM1','others'),
      col = c('blue','brown','purple','darkgreen','orange','cyan','grey'),
      pch=21,bty='n',cex=0.75)
```



```
## Second mode:
map(ceof, ip=2, projection="+proj=robin",
    main='EOF#2 of ERA5 and simulated low record-breaking annual rainfall recurrences')
```

2 of ERA5 and simulated low record-breaking annual rainfall recurrences


```
plot(coredata(ceof)[,2],main='PC#2',col=col)
points(1,ceof[1,2],pch=19,col='red',cex=1.5)
grid()
```


For precipitation, the results from common EOF evaluation suggests that the CMIP results do not correspond well with ERA5. The leading mode is by far the most important feature (99% of the variance). The greatest spatial weights are found over the northern Barents Sea, a region where sea-ice is retreating. The disappearance of sea-ice affects the air-sea moisture fluxes. The spread between different results for ζ for runs with one GCM is of similar magnitude as the model differences, but ERA5 (0.059) is slightly outside this range (0.055–0.0585).

The second mode is associated with little variance (0.04%), with strongest weights in the Tropics, and the results for ERA5 are well within the model spread.

```
y <- list2field(gcm.results,it='high.pr.future')
```

```
## Warning in matrix(rep(NA, n * nxy), n + 1, nxy): data length [3258720] is not a
## sub-multiple or multiple of the number of rows [311]
```

```
y <- subset(y,it=2:307)
m2 <- map(y,colbar=list('precip.ipcc'),projection="+proj=robin",
          main='Projected future annual rainfall record-breaking recurrences')
```

Projected future annual rainfall record-breaking recurrences

Maps of simulated record high precipitation reveal patterns similar to those found in CMIP3 by Benestad (2006), with lower rates over dry parts of the sub-tropics. The models indicate higher ζ over parts of the Arctic.

```
map(m2 - m1,colbar=list(pal='precip.ipcc',breaks=seq(-20,20,by=1)),projection="+proj=robin",  
    main='Simulated change in record-high annual mean rainfall recurrences')
```

Simulated change in record-high annual mean rainfall recurrences

The differences between ζ for record-high annual precipitation totals in the future and the past indicate a general increase in the number of new record-breaking annual rainfall totals. A general picture of reductions over parts of the subtropics, but there are some hot spots of high numbers in the Arctic and over the Himalayas.

3.6.1 Maps of record-lows.

```
## Reduce the spatial dimensions of AR1 map to cope with memory limitations
low.Tp.ERA5.record.stats <- TP[['low']]
low.Tp.ERA5.record.stats <- regrid(low.Tp.ERA5.record.stats,is=high.T2m.ERA5.record.stats)
gcm.results[['ERA5']] <- low.Tp.ERA5.record.stats
print(table(unlist(
  lapply(strsplit(names(gcm.results[grep('low.pr.hist',names(gcm.results))]),
    split=".",fixed=TRUE),function(x) x[1])))
```

```
##
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##           5           40           1           38
## CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
```

```

##          3          3          3          1
##   CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##          1          1          6          10
## EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
##          3          1          2          3
##   GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H      HadGEM3-GC31-LL      INM-CM4-8
##          24          5          5          1
##   INM-CM5-0      IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G      KIOST-ESM
##          1          11          3          1
##   MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6      MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##          1          30          50          30
##   MRI-ESM2-0      NESM3      NorESM2-LM      NorESM2-MM
##          5          2          3          2
##   TaiESM1      UKESM1-0-LL
##          1          14

```

```
y <- list2field(gcm.results,it='low.pr.hist')
```

```
## Warning in matrix(rep(NA, n * nxy), n + 1, nxy): data length [3258720] is not a
## sub-multiple or multiple of the number of rows [311]
```

```
m1 <- map(subset(y,it=2:307),colbar=list(pal='t2m'),projection="+proj=robin",
          main='Historical annual rainfall low record-breaking recurrences')
```

Historical annual rainfall low record-breaking recurrences


```
ceof <- EOF(y,anomaly=FALSE)
print(100*attr(ceof,'eigenvalues')^2/attr(ceof,'tot.var'))

## [1] 98.935016269 0.067304948 0.033193455 0.019027587 0.017407536
## [6] 0.015024821 0.014865453 0.012068359 0.011423483 0.010525218
## [11] 0.010443471 0.009962319 0.009678012 0.009183008 0.008720390
## [16] 0.008493167 0.008297048 0.008046078 0.007743345 0.007590561

map(ceof,projection="+proj=robin",
    main='EOF#1 of ERA5 and simulated low record-breaking annual rainfall recurrences')
```


20 leading EOFs: 99.2 % of variance


```
mid <- unlist(
  lapply(strsplit(attr(ceof, 'ID'), split='.', fixed=TRUE), function(x) x[1]))
print(table(mid))
```

```
## mid
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##           5           40           1           38
##      CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##           3           3           3           1
##      CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##           1           1           6           10
##      EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
##           3           1           2           3
##      GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H      HadGEM3-GC31-LL      INM-CM4-8
##          24           5           5           1
##      INM-CM5-0      IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G      KIOST-ESM
##           1           11           3           1
##      MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6      MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##           1           30           50           30
```

##	MRI-ESM2-0	NESM3	NorESM2-LM	NorESM2-MM
##	5	2	3	2
##	TaiESM1	UKESM1-0-LL		
##	1	14		

```

nm <- length(rownames(table(mid)))
col <- rep('grey',length(index(ceof)))
col[grep('ACCESS',mid)] <- 'blue'
col[grep('CanESM5',mid)] <- "brown"
col[grep('GISS-E2',mid)] <- "purple"
col[grep('MIROC-ES2L',mid)] <- "darkgreen"
col[grep('MPI-ESM1-2-LR',mid)] <- "orange"
col[grep('UKESM1-0-LL',mid)] <- "cyan"
plot(coredata(ceof)[,1],main='PC#1',col=col)
points(1,ceof[1,1],pch=19,col='red',cex=1.5)
grid()
legend(250,0.055,
      c('ACCESS','CanESM5','GISS-E2','MIROC-ES2L','MPI-ESM1','UKESM1','others'),
      col = c('blue','brown','purple','darkgreen','orange','cyan','grey'),
      pch=21,bty='n',cex=0.75)

```



```
## Second mode:
map(ceof, ip=2, projection="+proj=robin",
    main='EOF#2 of ERA5 and simulated low record-breaking annual rainfall recurrences')
```

2 of ERA5 and simulated low record-breaking annual rainfall recurrences


```
plot(coredata(ceof)[,2],main='PC#2',col=col)
points(1,ceof[1,2],pch=19,col='red',cex=1.5)
grid()
```


For the simulation of record-breaking-recurrence of low precipitation, there is a substantial discrepancy between ERA5 and the CMIP6 ensemble. There is a significant variability in the results produced by individual models, but ERA5 (0.053) is slightly outside the simulated range (0.054–0.058). The spatial map associated with the common-EOF-based evaluation have strong weights for ζ over North Africa (Sahara) and South Africa (the Amazon). These are regions with questionable precipitation data in reanalyses.

A map of simulated future record-low annual precipitation total point to greatest ζ over the Amazon region, thus hinting to more drought conditions over regions that presently have rain forests.

```
y <- list2field(gcm.results,it='low.pr.future')
```

```
## Warning in matrix(rep(NA, n * nxy), n + 1, nxy): data length [3258720] is not a
## sub-multiple or multiple of the number of rows [311]
```

```
y <- subset(y,it=2:307)
```

```
m2 <- map(y,colbar=list(pal='dry2wet'),projection="+proj=robin",
          main='Projected future annual rainfall record-breaking low rainfall recurrences')
```

Projected future annual rainfall record-breaking low rainfall recurrences

Maps of differences.

```
map(m2 - m1,colbar=list(pal='dry2wet',breaks=seq(-14,14,by=2)),projection="+proj=robin",  
    main='Simulated change in record-low annual rainfall recurrences')
```

Simulated change in record-low annual rainfall recurrences

3.6.2 Maps of AR1.

```
## Reduce the spatial dimensions of AR1 map to cope with memory limitations
ar1.tp <- TP[['ar1']]
ar1.tp <- regrid(ar1.tp, is=high.Tp.ERA5.record.stats)
## Repeat as above
gcm.results[['ERA5']] <- ar1.tp
print(table(unlist(
  lapply(strsplit(names(gcm.results[grep('ar1.pr.hist', names(gcm.results))]),
    split=".", fixed=TRUE), function(x) x[1]))))
```

```
##
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##           5           40           1           38
##      CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##           3           3           3           1
##      CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##           1           1           6           10
```

```

## EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
##           3           1           2           3
##   GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H  HadGEM3-GC31-LL  INM-CM4-8
##           24           5           5           1
##   INM-CM5-0      IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G      KIOST-ESM
##           1           11           3           1
##   MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6      MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##           1           30           50           30
##   MRI-ESM2-0      NESM3      NorESM2-LM      NorESM2-MM
##           5           2           3           2
##   TaiESM1      UKESM1-0-LL
##           1           14

```

```
y <- list2field(gcm.results,it='ar1.pr.hist')
```

```
## Warning in matrix(rep(NA, n * nxy), n + 1, nxy): data length [3258720] is not a
## sub-multiple or multiple of the number of rows [311]
```

```
m1 <- map(subset(y,it=2:307),projection="+proj=robin",
          colbar=list(pal='t2m'),main='Historical annual rainfall AR1')
```

Historical annual rainfall AR1


```
ceof <- EOF(y,anomaly=FALSE)
print(100*attr(ceof,'eigenvalues')^2/attr(ceof,'tot.var'))

## [1] 13.1800271 10.9973667 3.0369005 2.1664704 1.6062450 1.2822898
## [7] 1.0836463 1.0245103 0.9061939 0.8599587 0.8126608 0.7245753
## [13] 0.6874965 0.6676809 0.6652886 0.6468055 0.5951805 0.5801129
## [19] 0.5772397 0.5641723

map(ceof,main='EOF#1 of ERA5 and simulated AR1 for annual rainfall',projection="+proj=robin")
```

EOF#1 of ERA5 and simulated AR1 for annual rainfall


```
par(new=FALSE)  
plot(ceof,what="var")
```

20 leading EOFs: 42.7 % of variance


```
mid <- unlist(
  lapply(strsplit(attr(ceof, 'ID'), split='.', fixed=TRUE), function(x) x[1]))
print(table(mid))
```

```
## mid
##      ACCESS-CM2      ACCESS-ESM1-5      BCC-CSM2-MR      CanESM5
##           5           40           1           38
##      CanESM5-CanOE      CESM2      CESM2-WACCM      CIESM
##           3           3           3           1
##      CMCC-CM2-SR5      CMCC-ESM2      CNRM-CM6-1      CNRM-ESM2-1
##           1           1           6           10
##      EC-Earth3-Veg-LR      FGOALS-f3-L      FGOALS-g3      FIO-ESM-2-0
##           3           1           2           3
##      GISS-E2-1-G      GISS-E2-1-H      HadGEM3-GC31-LL      INM-CM4-8
##          24           5           5           1
##      INM-CM5-0      IPSL-CM6A-LR      KACE-1-0-G      KIOST-ESM
##           1           11           3           1
##      MCM-UA-1-0      MIROC-ES2L      MIROC6      MPI-ESM1-2-LR
##           1           30           50           30
```

##	MRI-ESM2-0	NESM3	NorESM2-LM	NorESM2-MM
##	5	2	3	2
##	TaiESM1	UKESM1-0-LL		
##	1	14		

```

nm <- length(rownames(table(mid)))
col <- rep('grey',length(index(ceof)))
col[grep('ACCESS',mid)] <- 'blue'
col[grep('CanESM5',mid)] <- "brown"
col[grep('GISS-E2',mid)] <- "purple"
col[grep('MIROC-ES2L',mid)] <- "darkgreen"
col[grep('MPI-ESM1-2-LR',mid)] <- "orange"
col[grep('UKESM1-0-LL',mid)] <- "cyan"
plot(coredata(ceof)[,1],main='PC#1',col=col)
points(1,ceof[1,1],pch=19,col='red',cex=1.5)
grid()
legend(200,-0.055,
      c('ACCESS','CanESM5','GISS-E2','MIROC-ES2L','MPI-ESM1','UKESM1','others'),
      col = c('blue','brown','purple','darkgreen','orange','cyan','grey'),
      pch=21,bty='n',cex=0.75)

```

PC#1


```
## Second mode:  
map(ceof,ip=2,projection="+proj=robin",  
    main='EOF#2 of ERA5 and simulated AR1 for annual rainfall')
```

EOF#2 of ERA5 and simulated AR1 for annual rainfall


```
plot(coredata(ceof)[,2],main='PC#2',col=col)
points(1,ceof[1,2],pch=19,col='red',cex=1.5)
grid()
```


The leading mode of the common EOF for AR1 in the evaluation accounts for a modest fraction of the variance (13%), suggesting that there are many different spatial structures and a substantial degree of diversity between the models.

The models project a pronounced regional increase in AR1 for precipitation over the Barents Sea. This may be due to the retreat of sea ice. The common EOF evaluation indicates that the leading mode is associated with a relatively low proportion of the variance (< 20%) and suggests that there is a wide spread in the model simulation of the precipitation year-to-year dependence.

Plot maps of simulated future annual AR1 in precipitation:

```
y <- list2field(gcm.results,it='ar1.pr.future')
```

```
## Warning in matrix(rep(NA, n * nxy), n + 1, nxy): data length [3258720] is not a
## sub-multiple or multiple of the number of rows [311]
```

```
y <- subset(y,it=2:307)
m2 <- map(y,colbar=list(pal='t2m'),projection="+proj=robin",
          main='Projected future annual rainfall AR1')
```

Projected future annual rainfall AR1

the maps showing differences in AR1 of simulated annual precipitation between the past and the future indicate an increase over parts of the Arctic Ocean, which is likely associated with simulated retreating sea-ice cover.

```
map(m2 - m1, projection="+proj=robin",  
    main='Simulated change in record-high annual rainfall AR1')
```

Simulated change in record-high annual rainfall AR1

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